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MHD Flow of Viscos-Elastic and Thermal-Radiative Fluid in the Presence of Buoyancy Upshot over Oscillating Vertical Plates

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ABSTRACT

Numerical study of viscos-elastic and thermal radiative fluid in the presence of buoyancy distribution of effects over oscillating vertical plates has been examined. The governing coupled non-dimensional partial differential equations and their boundaries conditions were transformed into dimensionless form using appropriate dimensionless quantities. An implicit finite difference method was applied to find the numerical solution of the dimensionless partial differential equations subject to the given initials and boundary conditions. The numerical results were displayed using line graphs. The comparison for the validation of the present study and that of the previous one was also shown graphically. From the graph of the comparison it was clearly noticed that there is complete agreement between the present study and that of previous one. From the outcome of the results of present study, it was found that Viscos-elastic parameter (α), micro-polar (β), Porosity Parameter (K) and ratio of mass transfer (N) improve fluid velocity while the opposite trend was observed for magnetic parameter (M). Similarly, the temperature profile gets enlarged with the rise in dissipative parameter (μ), Viscos-elastic parameter (α), Buoyancy parameter (γ) and radiative parameter (σ) and reverse is the case is with the rise in prandlt number (Pr). Furthermore, the skin friction gets bigger with the rise in buoyancy parameter (γ) and viscos-elastic parameter (α). Also Micro-polar parameter (β) and viscos-elastic parameter (α) boosts the nusselt number. It is exciting to report that the present study may be applied in thermal management system, power generation, heat exchangers Electronic cooling and so on.

Keywords

Viscos-elastic, buoyancy effects, Thermal Radiative, Oscillating vertical Plates

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many liquids that display both viscos and elastic properties, such liquids includes oils, some paints, polymer solution and some organic liquids. These types of liquids are called viscoelastic fluids. The research on these types of liquids has received many attentions by the researchers. The viscoelastic fluid flow magneto hydrodynamics (MHD) in vertical plates has been the basic of several industrial science and engineering applications. Depending on kinetic characteristics of the flow field under consideration and direction of the flow viscos elastic properties can boost or slow down heat transfer rate. The impact of heat mass transfer viscos dissipation and joule heating in a boundary layer flow mixed convection of an electrically conducting incompressible Nano-fluid was carried out by [1]. Furthermore, the influence of viscos elastic fluid on MHD slip Darcy umber boundary layer heat mass transfer in non-

linear stretchable surface in porous medium viscous dissipation and thermal radiation was analyzed by [2]. Similarly, the effects of Non-Newton viscous elastic fluid MHD over stretched magnetized surface was analyzed by [3]. Additionally, the influence of MHD slip flow Nano-fluid over a vertical porous plate heat transfer in the presence of buoyancy effect was analyzed by [4] and stated that, the temperature and velocity profile are enhanced with the rise in mixed Convection parameter. Moreover, the effects of MHD heat mass transfer flow viscous energy dissipation in the presence of chemical reaction in a past inclined porous plate was carried out by [5] and revealed that, the temperature and velocity profile are boosted with rise in Peclet energy and Eckert number. Also, the influence of MHD heat mass transfer convective boundary condition in the presence of buoyancy and chemical reaction was done by [6] and reported that velocity profile enhanced as ratio of thermal buoyancy to mass buoyancy shrinks.

The impact of MHD Soret and Dufour heat mass transfer in the presence buoyancy effect due to the ramped temperature was carried out by [7] and reported that, the buoyancy parameter has improving effects on velocity and temperature profile. [8] Investigated the impact of MHD steady flow of Maxwell viscos-elastic fluid in flat porous plate with heat generation and radiation and reported that radiation parameter causes rise in temperature profile. Similarly, [9] analyzed the impact of MHD heat mass flow past an inclined porous plate in the presence of chemical reaction and concluded that the radiation parameter rises the fluid temperature. The impact of MHD mixed convection of flow of second grade fluid past a vertical infinite plate with viscous dissipation and joule heating was studied by [10]. The influence of MHD heat source in permeable structure under the influence chemical reaction and oscillatory structure was investigated by [11]. Likewise, the impact of MHD thermal radiation and Casson fluid in the presence viscos-elastic and viscous dissipation was analyzed by [12] and reported that the Nusselt number is enhanced with the rise radiation parameter. Also, [13] investigated the influence of MHD viscos-elastic unsteady flow past a constant slanted in the presence viscous dissipation, radiation and chemical reaction and reported that viscous-elastic parameter boosts velocity profile.

The impact MHD heat mass transfer flow in porous medium in the presence of chemical reaction in vertical moving plate was analyzed by [14] and reported that thermal buoyancy parameter boosts temperature profile. Additionally, [15] analyzed the effects of MHD viscos-elastic fluid bounded by an oscillating flat plate in slip flow regime and discovered that the velocity profile gets enhanced with the rise in buoyancy due to mass transfer and elastic elements. Similarly, [16] investigated the impact of buoyancy and radiation on MHD heat mass transfer free convection flow of boundary layer across a stretchable porous sheet. The impact of Casson fluid MHD heat and mass transfer with variable properties in the presence non-linear thermal radiation over an elastic sheet was carried out by [17]. Also, the impact of viscous elastic radiative flow in an inclined porous medium in the presence diffusion thermo was analyzed by [18] and revealed that viscous-elasticity enhances velocity. Furthermore, [19] studied the similarity solution of MHD flow unsteady viscous incompressible fluid in an inclined porous surface with ohmic heating

The main objective of the present study is to extend the model of [20] where buoyancy reaction on unsteady MHD free convective flow of micro polar fluid over an oscillating vertical plate has been analyzed. The present study tends to do extension by incorporating viscos-elastic parameter into the momentum equation, under the consideration of the impact of buoyancy and radiation. Therefore the study will be able to numerically examine the influence of viscos-elastic, buoyancy and radiation.

2. Mathematical Analysis

The influence of viscos-elastics buoyancy and radiation over an oscillating vertical plates has been studied. The physical channels of the parallel vertical plates are illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 1: Geometry of the Problem

Let x^* be carried along the plate upward direction and y^* is taken normal to the plate. There is uniform magnetic field applied transversely to the plate and induced magnetic field is not considered. Both the initially temperature T^* and that of fluid T_w^* are both considered to be the same. When $t > 0$, the plate temperature increases to T_w^* which is maintain like that leading to the convection currents flowing close the plate. Under these conditions the flow variables are function of x^* ad y^* only. The problem is now governed by the following partial differential equations:

$$\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial t^*} = \nu(1 + \beta) \frac{\partial^2 u^*}{\partial y^{*2}} - \alpha \left[\frac{\partial^2 u^*}{\partial y^{*2} \partial t^*} \right] + g\beta^*(T^* - T_\infty^*) - \frac{\sigma\mu_0^2 H_0^2}{\rho} - \frac{M\nu u^*}{K^*} \quad (1)$$

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T^*}{\partial t^*} = k \frac{\partial^2 T^*}{\partial y^{*2}} + \mu \left[\frac{du^*}{dy^*} \right]^2 - \sigma T^* \quad (2)$$

The following are non-dimensional form of boundary and initial conditions

$$t^* \leq 0: u^* = 0, T^* = T_0, \text{ for all } 0 \leq y^* \leq L$$

$$t^* > 0 \begin{cases} u^* = \frac{u}{U_0} \cos \omega t, T^* = \gamma T_w^*, \text{ at } y^* = 0 \\ u^* = 0, T^* = T_\infty^*, \text{ at } y^* = \infty \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In order to make (1), (2) and (3) dimensionless, below is the non-dimensional variables

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} U_0 = (\nu g \beta \Delta T)^{\frac{1}{3}}, L = \left(\frac{g \beta \Delta T}{\nu^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{3}}, T_R = \left(\frac{g \beta \Delta T}{\nu^2} \right)^{-\frac{2}{3}} \\ \Delta T = T_w^* - T_\infty^*, t = \frac{t^*}{T_R}, y = \frac{y^*}{L} \\ u = \frac{u^*}{U_0}, K = \frac{K^*}{\nu T_R}, \theta = \frac{T^* - T_\infty^*}{T_w^* - T_\infty^*} \\ Pr = \frac{\mu C_p}{k}, Ec = \frac{U_0^2}{C_p \Delta T}, N = \frac{\beta^*}{\beta(T_w^* - T_\infty^*)}, M = \frac{\rho \mu_0^2 H_0^2 T_R}{\rho} \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is applied to change the equations (1) to (3) into dimensionless form as follows:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = (1 + \beta) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \alpha \left[\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial y^2 \partial t} \right] + Nu - \left(M + \frac{1}{K} \right) u \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + \mu \left[\frac{du}{dy} \right]^2 - \sigma \theta \quad (6)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} t \geq 0: u = 0, \theta = \gamma, \text{ for all } y \\ \text{For } t > 0: u = \cos wt, \theta = \rho, \text{ at } y = 0 \\ u = 0, \theta \rightarrow 0, \text{ at } y \rightarrow \infty \end{array} \right\} \quad (7)$$

2.1 Method of the Solution

Solving equations (5) and (6) subject to the initial and boundary conditions (7), implicit finite difference is employed and applying it on equation (5) gives:

$$\frac{u_i^{n+1} - u_i^n}{\Delta t} = \frac{u_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2u_i^{n+1} + u_{i-1}^{n+1}}{2(Dy)^2} + M_2 \frac{u_{i+1}^n - 2u_i^n + u_{i-1}^n}{2(Dy)^2} - s \left[\frac{u_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2u_i^{n+1} + u_{i-1}^{n+1} - u_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2u_i^n + u_{i-1}^n}{\Delta t 2(Dy)^2} \right] + N(u_i^{n+1} - u_i^n) - M_3(u_i^{n+1} - u_i^n) \quad (8)$$

Where $M_2 = (1 + \beta)$ and $M_3 = (1 + \beta)$

Letting $\Delta y = h, \Delta t = k$ and $r = \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta y)^2}$ and simplification we have:

$$A_1 u_{i-1}^{n+1} + A_2 u_i^{n+1} + A_3 u_{i+1}^{n+1} = A_4 u_{i-1}^n + A_5 u_i^n + A_6 u_{i+1}^n \quad (9)$$

Similarly, applying the same method on equation (6) then we have:

$$B_1 u_{i-1}^{n+1} + B_2 u_i^{n+1} + B_3 u_{i+1}^{n+1} = B_4 u_{i-1}^n + B_5 u_i^n + B_6 u_{i+1}^n + 2Pr\gamma [u_i^{n+1} - u_i^n]^2 \quad (10)$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= -M_2 r, A_2 = 2 + 2M_2 r + 2kM_3 - 2KN - \frac{2\alpha}{h^2}, A_3 = -M_2 r \\ A_4 &= M_2 r + \frac{2\alpha}{h^2}, A_5 = 2 + 2M_2 r + 2kM_2 - 2kN - 2rM_3 - \frac{2\alpha}{h^2}, A_6 = M_2 r \\ B_1 &= -r, B_2 = 2r + 2Pr + 2rkPr, B_3 = -r \\ B_4 &= r, B_5 = 2Pr - 2r - 2\gamma kPr, B_6 = r \end{aligned}$$

In the above simplification, $r = \frac{k}{h^2}$, h and k are mesh size along y and time direction respectively.

Index i denotes the grid points with y coordinate and subscript n represent value of time t , $t = n\Delta$, where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. In equation (10) and (9) taking $i=1(1)n$ and using the initial and boundary conditions (7) the following system of equations is gotten:

$$A_i X_i = B_i \quad i = 1(1)n \quad (11)$$

A_i are matrices of order n while B_i are column matrices with n components. The solution of the above system of equations is obtained using MATLAB for both velocity and temperature. The results are calculated and shown graphically using various parameters. Being the very significant physical parameters for this type boundary layer's flow the skin friction and nusselt number are evaluated when the value of velocity and temperature known, therefore the skin friction and nusselt number are obtained as:

The skin friction (τ) at the plates is defined as:

$$\tau = \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right]_{y=0,1} \tag{12}$$

The Nusselt number (N_u) at the plate is defined as:

$$N_u = \left[\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right]_{y=0,1} \tag{13}$$

3. Results Validation

The analysis to validate the present study is shown in the diagram below. The diagram clearly shows that there is an excellent agreement between the present study and that of [20]

Figure 2: Comparison between the works of [20] and present study when $\sigma = 0, \gamma = 0, \alpha = 0$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of MHD Flow of Viscos-Elastic and Thermal-Radiative Fluid in the presence of Buoyancy Effects over an Oscillating Vertical Plates has been studied. The study has been able to show graphically the presentation of velocity, temperature, skin friction and nusselt number respectively. The influence of necessary and relevant parameters of the flow on velocity, temperature, skin friction and nusselt number has been shown using line graph. The study has adopted the following parameters and their default values: $M = 1, Pr = 0.71, \alpha = 1, \mu = 1, \sigma = 1, N = 1, \beta = 1, \gamma = 1, K = 1$

Figure 3. Impact of α on Velocity Profile

Figure 4: Impact of β on Velocity Profile.

Figure 5: Impact of K on Velocity Profile.

Figure 6: Impact of M on Velocity Profile.

Figure 7: Impact of N on Velocity Profile.

As it is clearly seen **Figure 3**, illustrates the boosting behavior of viscos-elastic parameter (α) on velocity profile, the boosting effects is due to the internal heat generation. Similarly, **Figure 4&5** depicts that velocity profile is reasonably enhanced with the rise of both micro-polar (β), and Porosity Parameter (K), parameters respectively. Additionally, **Figure 6&7** displays the influence of magnetic parameter (M), and ratio of mass transfer (N), respectively. From the **Figure 6** the velocity profile gets depressed with the intensification of magnetic parameter (M), while the reverse trend is observed in **Figure 7** with ratio of mass transfer (N).

Figure 8: Impact of μ on Temperature Profile.

Figure 9: Impact of Pr on Temperature Profile.

Figure 10: Impact of σ on Temperature Profile.

Figure 11. Impact of γ on Temperature Profile

Figure 8, depicts the enhancing behavior of viscos dissipative parameter (μ) on temperature profile, this is to say that the temperature profile gets heightened with the rise in viscos dissipative parameter(μ). Furthermore, **Figure 9** shows that, the temperature profile gets lowered with the rise in prandlt number(Pr), while the reverse behavior is observed in **Figure 10** with the rise in radiative parameter (σ). Buoyancy parameter (γ), describes the behavior of directly proportional on temperature profile, this is to say that, rising the parameter improves temperature profile and vice versa in **Figure 11**.

Figure 12 Impact of α & γ on τ_0

Figure 13: Impact of α & γ on τ_1 .

Figure 14 Impact of β & γ on τ_0

Figure 15: Impact of β & γ on τ_1

Figure 16 Impact of β & γ on Nu_0

Figure 17: Impact of β & γ on Nu_1

Figure 18 Impact of α & γ on Nu_0

Figure 19: Impact of β & γ on Nu_1

Figure 12 and 13, illustrates the effects of viscos-elastic parameter (α) and buoyancy parameter (γ) on skin friction. It is clearly noticed from the both figures that the skin friction gets higher with the rise in both parameters. Moreover, the skin friction in both Figure 14 and 15 gets enlarged with rise in in both Buoyancy and gets lowered with rise in micropolar parameter (β). In Figure 16 and 17 display the impact of micro-polar parameter (β) and buoyancy parameter γ on nusselt number. From the both figures the nusselt number rises with the rise in micro-polar parameter (β) and diminishes with the rise in buoyancy parameter (γ). Furthermore, there is also growth in nusselt number in Figure 18 and 19 with the intensification of viscos-elastic parameter α and reduction with the rises in buoyancy parameter (γ).

5. CONCLUSION

The MHD flow of viscos-elastic and thermal-radiative fluid in the presence of buoyancy upshot over oscillating vertical plates has been studied. The results were presented in the form velocity, temperature, skin friction and nusselt number. The highpoints of the present study are summarized as follows:

- i. Viscos-elastic parameter (α) micro-polar (β) Porosity Parameter (K) ad Ratio of mass transfer (N) improve fluid velocity while magnetic parameter (M) diminishes it
- ii. The temperature profile gets enhanced with the rise in viscos dissipative parameter (μ) Buoyancy parameter (γ) radiative parameter σ and reverse of the case is seen with the rise in prandlt number (Pr)
- iii. The skin friction is enhanced with the rise in Buoyancy parameter (γ) and viscos-elastic parameter (α). Similarly, the nusselt number is enlarged with rise in micro-polar parameter (β) and viscos-elastic parameter (α).

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Author Contributions

Faruk Abdullahi: Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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APPENDIX

Table of Nomenclature

Symbols	Description	Symbols	Description
C_p	Specific heat constant pressure	C^*	Specific Concentration Near the
Plate	C_∞^* Ambient fluid Concentration	Ec	Eckert Number
g	Accelerature due to gravity	k	Thermal Conductivity
N	Ratio of Mass Transfer	P_r	Prandlt Number
Sc	Schmidt Number	T^*	Temperature of the fluid Close the
Plate	T_∞^* Amient fluid Temperature	t^*	Dimensional time
β^*	Coefficient of Species expansion	μ	Viscos Dissipative parameter
ν	Kinematic Viscosity	ρ	Density
u	Non-dimensional velocity	σ	Dissipative parameter
γ	Viscos-elastic Parameter	K	Porosity Parameter
α	Buoyancy parameter	σ	Radiative parameter

θ^*	Dimensional temperature	β	Micro-polar parameter
t	Dimensionless time	y	Dimensionless distance
M	Magetic field parameter	u^*	Dimensional Velocity
τ_0	Skin friction at $y = 0$	τ_1	Skin friction at $y = 1$
Nu_0	Nusselt number $y = 0$	Nu_1	Nusselt number $y = 1$